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7 **Deceiving predators: linking distraction behavior with nest survival in a ground-**
8 **nesting bird**

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22

23 **LAY SUMMARY**

24 Ground-nesting birds employ different defensive behaviors as part of their anti-predator
25 strategies because they nest in sites easily accessible to a wide range of predators. We
26 analyzed defensive behavior and nest survival in the Kentish Plover. Nests in which

27 parents invested more on defense survived longer. Females performed riskier defensive
28 behaviors than males. Increased risk in offspring defense is advantageous in terms of
29 individual fitness.

30

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56

57 **ABSTRACT**

58 Individual behavior that minimizes predation risk is favored by natural selection.
59 Ground-nesting birds employ different defensive behaviors as part of their anti-predator
60 strategies because they nest where a wide range of predators have access. We
61 investigated the influence of distraction displays on breeding success in the Kentish
62 Plover, *Charadrius alexandrinus*, in order to explore the role of the defensive behavior
63 on nest survival. We quantified the intensity of defensive behavior of adult plovers in
64 response to nest disturbance caused by an approaching researcher, by ranking display
65 types according to the intensity and exposure to predation. We also examined sex
66 differences in nest defense to determine whether the existence, intensity and consistency
67 of individual defensive behaviors could have an impact on nest survival. We used the
68 nest survival model in Program MARK to estimate daily survival rates of nests and to
69 examine the influence of temporal, behavioral and habitat variables on nest success. Our
70 results show a positive correlation between male and female defense behaviors within
71 pairs and that nests in which parents invested more on defense survived longer.
72 Nevertheless, there were differences in the risks assumed by the two members of
73 breeding pairs in nest defense, with females performing riskier defensive behaviors than
74 males. The top-ranked nest survival models included combined additive effects of site,

75 season, habitat type, nest exposure, and the defense behavioral response of females as
76 best predictors. Finally, our study highlights that increased risk assumption in offspring
77 defense is advantageous in terms of individual fitness.

78

79 **Keywords:**

80 *Charadrius alexandrinus*; defense investment; distraction displays; MARK; plovers;
81 predation risk.

82

83 **INTRODUCTION**

84 Animals avoid predation through different adaptations and strategies such as early
85 predator detection, cryptic coloration or flushing behavior (Magnhagen 1991; Koivula
86 and Rönkä 1998; Colwell 2010). As a consequence, individual behavior that minimizes
87 predation risk is favored by natural selection (Lima and Dill, 1990). From the prey
88 perspective, defensive tactics are either based on fleeing or remaining motionless (Lima
89 and Dill 1990). Nevertheless, despite the obvious advantages of flushing behavior
90 (Burrell and Colwell 2012), potential preys may approach their predators for different
91 reasons (Dugatkin and Godin 1992). For instance, birds may thus proceed so as to
92 evaluate the actual threat posed by predators (predator risk assessment), and act
93 accordingly. In general, predator approaching increases the chances of being preyed
94 upon and thus, this behavior can only be understood from a cost-benefit perspective
95 (Dugatkin and Godin 1992), with parental offspring defense being one of the most
96 prominent examples of this paradoxical behavior (Anderson et al. 1980).

97 Some birds have developed particular modalities of parental defense based on
98 performing displays with the aim to divert predator attention from offspring (Gochfeld

99 1984; Sordahl 1986; Caro 2005; Colwell 2010) and direct it towards fake nests or easy
100 preys. This can be achieved through the display of dishonest signals concerning their
101 physical condition or by mimicking a reduced ability to escape. Given that this
102 defensive behavior is costly (Brunton 1986; Sordahl 1990a), birds are expected to trade-
103 off the burden of a higher predation risk for increased offspring survival (Montgomerie
104 and Weatherhead, 1988; Dugatkin and Godin 1992; Frid and Dill 2002).

105 The behavior of incubating birds has a significant impact on breeding success. Previous
106 studies have shown that certain adult behaviors (e.g. flushing behavior of incubating
107 adults or the frequency of incubation recesses) are clearly linked to a decrease in
108 predation risk of both adult and nests (Koivula and Rönkä 1998; Amat and Masero
109 2004a; Smith et al. 2012; Gómez-Serrano and López-López 2014). Nevertheless, the
110 impact of the defensive behavior on the breeding success has received little attention so
111 far (Caro 2005; Smith and Wilson 2010). Moreover, the inclusion of these behavioral
112 variables into nest survival models remains unexplored (Colwell et al. 2011).

113 Ground-nesting birds' nests are accessible to a wide range of predators. Therefore, it is
114 expected that defensive behaviors will play a major role in nest survival (Gochfeld
115 1984; Montgomerie and Weatherhead 1988; Rytönen 2002). Shorebirds employ
116 different types of defensive behaviors as part of their anti-predator strategies (Gochfeld
117 1984; Sordahl 1986; Larsen 1991; Colwell 2010), performing both distraction displays
118 as well as aggressive mobbing (Simmons, 1955a; Jónsson and Gunnarsson 2010). To
119 address the role of the defensive behaviors on nest survival, we explored the influence
120 of distraction displays on breeding success in a ground nesting bird, the Kentish Plover,
121 *Charadrius alexandrinus*. To this end, we quantified the intensity of defensive behavior
122 of adult plovers in response to nest disturbance caused by an approaching researcher.

123 We also examined differences in nest defense within breeding pairs to determine
124 whether the existence, intensity and consistency of individual defensive behaviors have
125 a significant impact on nest survival. Finally, we included the defensive behavior of
126 adults in nest survival models at the same level as habitat covariates, with the aim to
127 explore the relative contribution of these behaviors on nest success.

128 Specifically, we tested whether 1) investment in nest defense differs between males and
129 females within pairs; 2) nest survival is correlated with the intensity and frequency of
130 defensive behavior exhibited by one or both members of the pair; and 3) nest survival
131 models that take into account variables of defensive behavior fit better than those that
132 only include environmental variables.

133

134 **MATERIALS AND METHODS**

135 **Study Species**

136 The Kentish Plover is a ground nesting shorebird distributed along Eurasia and Africa
137 (BirdLife International 2015). Kentish Plovers may breed in different habitats
138 throughout their range, including coastal beaches, river banks with pebbles, sand bars,
139 salt pans, and salt flats (Fraga and Amat 1996; Oltra and Gómez-Serrano 1997; Colwell
140 et al. 2005). Sandy beaches are an important natural breeding habitat for Kentish Plover,
141 but beaches are also highly valued by humans for recreational purposes. The study
142 species is listed as threatened in the Valencian Community (Eastern Spain) since 2013
143 where this study has been conducted. Along the Mediterranean coast of Spain, its
144 population decline is attributed, at least partially, to habitat degradation associated with
145 an increase of human disturbance (Oltra and Gómez-Serrano, 1997; Figuerola and Amat
146 2003; Figuerola et al. 2005). Kentish Plover exhibits biparental incubation, with females

147 and males usually incubating during the day and at night, respectively (Fraga and Amat
148 1996; Kosztolányi and Székely 2002; Kosztolanyi et al. 2003; Amat and Masero
149 2004b). Predation is one of the major causes of nest failure (Fraga and Amat 1996;
150 Norte and Ramos 2004; Saalfeld et al. 2011; Gómez-Serrano and López-López 2014).
151 In the studied beaches, predation affects from 6 to 25% of nests initiated (Serradal 6%;
152 Almenara 25%; Punta 20%), and the main predators are the Yellow-legged Gull (*Larus*
153 *michahellis*) and mammals (especially hedgehogs, *Erinaceus europaeus*) (authors
154 unpub. data). Nesting plovers usually perform a variety of distraction displays as part of
155 their antipredator strategies (Simmons, 1951; Cramp and Simmons 1983).

156

157 **Study Area**

158 We sampled three beaches in the Castellón and Valencia provinces (Eastern Spain):
159 Serradal (Castellón de la Plana, 40° 00' N, 0° 01' E), Almenara (39° 43' N, 0° 11' W)
160 and Punta (Valencia 39° 18' N, 0° 17' W). All three sites have natural dune vegetation.
161 Punta (1.2 km in length) and Serradal (1.1 km) are natural sandy beaches, whereas
162 Almenara (2.3 km) is a natural beach of mixed sandy areas with gravel and pebbles. The
163 three coastal areas benefit from different types of legal protection according to
164 European and regional legislation. At these three sites, Kentish plovers nest primarily
165 on embryonic shifting dunes and annual vegetation of drift lines, but also in grasslands
166 of small annual plants that grow on deep sandy areas among dry interdunal depressions
167 (Gómez-Serrano and López-López, 2014). Dominant plants within these habitats
168 include *Elymus farctus*, *Ammophila arenaria*, *Medicago marina*, *Lotus creticus*,
169 *Otanthus maritimus*, *Pancratium maritimum*, *Sporobolus pungens* and *Cakile maritima*
170 (Gómez-Serrano and López-López 2014).

171 The three beaches are subject to different intensities of human disturbance. Serradal is a
172 beach frequented by people for leisure (> 10 people/km/hour; authors' unpubl. data). On
173 the other hand, Almenara has an intermediate level of human disturbance, with lower
174 human presence as compared to Serradal (1 - 5 people/km/hour; authors' unpubl. data).
175 Finally, Punta is a bird sanctuary with restricted access, where human presence is
176 almost negligible (managers and occasional trespassers) (Gómez-Serrano and López-
177 López 2014).

178

179 **Field Procedure**

180 Our study was conducted during two different periods. Firstly, we carried out research
181 at Serradal between 1993 and 2001, during each breeding season; secondly, between
182 2007 and 2008 at the three study sites simultaneously. The same observer recorded all
183 data across study areas and years, so there was no bias due to variability among
184 observers.

185 Kentish plover nests were found by systematically searching beaches and dune systems
186 from early March to late July. Once a nest was found, it was individually geolocated
187 (i.e., including GPS location and a brief schema of close vegetation and objects) and
188 visited every 3-5 days to monitor nest fate. We marked each egg so as to identify it
189 during subsequent visits and to record egg-turning activity. There were no differences in
190 the rate of nest visits across years and study sites. Kentish plovers were not marked in
191 this study.

192

193 **Nest Fate**

194 Nests were considered successful when at least one egg hatched. Evidence of hatching
195 included presence of (i) chicks; (ii) eggshell evidence (i.e. small fragments of detached
196 eggshell membranes in nest scrape) (Mabee, 1997; Mabee et al. 2006) or (iii) adults
197 with chicks or adults performing distraction displays when nests scrapes were empty
198 close to hatching date. Evidence of predation included (i) partially consumed eggs in
199 nests scrapes or their surroundings, (ii) presence of a mixture of yolk and sand from
200 broken eggs, or (iii) the disappearance of eggs before expected hatching date.

201 The absence of adults in the vicinity of the nest and the lack of response from nesting
202 birds (i.e., distraction displays), were important aspects of this study. Therefore, we
203 carefully monitored nest activity during each visit. We considered that nests were active
204 when they were attended by adults for incubation tasks. Evidence of nest activity
205 included the observation of: (i) incubating parents; (ii) incubating parents flushing from
206 the nest when the observer approached; (iii) adults performing distraction displays
207 against potential predators (including researchers) in the vicinity of the nest; (iv) egg-
208 turning since the previous visit; (v) normal development according to the egg-flotation
209 schedule (Mabee et al. 2006); and (vi) a high density of plover footprints on the sand
210 around the nest scrape. Egg-turning activity was monitored by two measurements: egg
211 position and rotation. To this end, eggs were individually marked in its central part the
212 first time they were found, and the position of the mark was recorded every visit. In
213 each control we took a photograph of the nest (geographically oriented) and we
214 recorded the position of each egg. We use these photographs to check for changes in the
215 position and angle of the eggs within the nest between consecutive visits. The
216 movements of eggs obtained by both methods were used as evidence that nests were
217 active, given the frequency with which they were rotated by parents during incubation.

218 We considered that nests were deserted if there was no evidence of the formerly
219 described signs of activity, confirming this fate on subsequent visits. For failed
220 unsuccessful nests, we assumed that either predation or desertion had occurred halfway
221 between the last visit when nest activity was recorded and the subsequent one, when no
222 activity was observed.

223 We assessed laying date according to clutch size and laying interval for the Kentish
224 Plover (Fraga and Amat 1996; Colwell 2006; Page et al. 2009). We assumed that nests
225 with one egg had been initiated on the same day they were encountered, whereas those
226 with two eggs and a third one observed in the following visit were considered to have
227 been started the day before. Laying date in nests with complete clutches (i.e. with three
228 eggs, the modal clutch size, or two eggs without a third one on a subsequent visit) was
229 estimated using the hatching date or through the egg-flotation pattern (Van Paassen et
230 al. 1984; Mabee et al. 2006). Alternatively, when the laying date was unknown (i.e. the
231 nest was found with complete clutch) but the Plover's courtship scrape was previously
232 recorded (Muir and Colwell 2010), we assumed that laying date had taken place
233 halfway between the last visit with the empty nest scrape and the following visit with
234 complete clutch.

235 For each nest, we calculated survival rate as the number of days elapsed since the laying
236 of the first egg until the hatching of last egg, or until predation or desertion. The average
237 maximum number of days that nests typically survive is 31 (Amat and Masero 2004a).

238

239 **Habitat Measurements**

240 We recorded nest locations using a handheld GPS. Subsequently, we corrected the
241 coordinates with an ortho-rectified aerial photograph with the images loaded into GIS

242 software. This procedure allowed us to precisely assess nest distance to the seashore.
243 For this purpose, we used different aerial photographs of study sites, in an attempt to
244 achieve a match as close as possible between the year images were taken and the date of
245 nest inventory. Each nest was assigned to one of the following habitat types as
246 described by Gómez-Serrano and López-López (2014): i) tidal debris (i.e., beach area
247 outside the tidal zone where scattered organic and inorganic remains washed by the sea
248 accumulate; ii) embryonic shifting dunes (i.e., first stages of dune build-up, consisting
249 of sand ripples or raised sand bars on the upper parts of the beach); iii) shifting dunes
250 (mobile dunes forming seaward dunes, typically following embryonic shifting dunes);
251 and iv) semi-fixed dunes (i.e., dunes with a low relief at the rear of shifting dunes with
252 vegetation dominated by geophytes and small sized scrubs). We assigned nests located
253 in grasslands of small annual plants that grow on deep sand areas among dry inter-dunal
254 depressions to the latter habitat type.

255 Plovers tend to nest on bare sites in order to enhance early detection of predators
256 (Burger, 1987; Amat and Masero 2004a; Muir and Colwell 2010; Saalfeld et al. 2011;
257 Gómez-Serrano and López-López 2014). On sandy beaches, such environments are
258 usually found between the seashore and the first shifting dunes. This is an area more
259 exposed to adverse weather events (e.g. sea storms, flooding, etc.) but also to the sea
260 breeze, which may have a cooling effect that alleviates heat stress on eggs and
261 incubating adults (authors' unpubl. data). In order to evaluate the influence of these
262 environmental factors on nest survival, the degree of nest exposure was assigned to two
263 categories: exposed nests (i.e., unprotected nests usually lying within tidal debris,
264 embryonic shifting dunes, shifting dunes and interdunal corridors); unexposed nests
265 (i.e., protected nests usually located within semi-fixed dunes and interdunal

266 depressions). We also recorded the substrate type for each nest site and classified it as
267 sand or pebbles. We included substrates consisting of a sand and pebble mixture in the
268 latter category. Finally, we added a binary covariate of management based on the
269 presence or absence (i. e. bird sanctuary) of human disturbance at study sites.

270

271 **Nest Defence**

272 Typically, Kentish plover distraction behavior consists of two components. Initially,
273 when a potential predator approaches the nest, the incubating adult crouch-runs away
274 with legs bent, neck depressed and body horizontal to the ground in order to go by
275 unnoticed (Simmons 1951). Subsequently, if predation risk persists, adults may perform
276 distraction displays to lure the predator away from the nest (Cramp and Simmons 1983).

277 In the present study, distraction behavior of adult plovers was recorded in response to
278 nest disturbance caused by an approaching researcher. We walked in a straight line
279 towards the nest from a distance of 150 m at constant speed (50 m/min), in order to
280 avoid the bias associated with flush initiation distance (Blumstein 2003). When the
281 incubating adult left the nest, we recorded its behavior and monitored both parents
282 separately as we approached the nest. Once we reached it, we stood close to the nest for
283 two minutes, during which we recorded birds' behavior. Subsequently, we recorded
284 habitat and nest characteristics and, after that, we walked away.

285 We ranked display types from little to extreme on a subjective scale according to the
286 intensity (i.e., energy expenditure) and exposure to predation (Sordahl 1986; Bruntom
287 1990; Pavel et al. 2000). Both sexes, sexed by differences in plumage characteristics,
288 were scored on an ordinal scale ranging from 0 to 6, with higher values reflecting
289 greater proximity (i.e., higher exposure to predators) and higher intensity of defense

290 (Brunton 1990; Møller 1984; Lord et al. 2001; Møller and Nielsen 2014). For each nest
291 approach, we only used the highest value of the ranked behavior for each parent for
292 subsequent analysis.

293 Defensive behaviors may be increased in frequency and (or) intensity as predators
294 approach offspring (Byrkjedal 1989; Caro 2005). Moreover, displays performed closest
295 to predators involve greater predation risk (Lima and Dill 1990). For these reasons, we
296 considered the distance between the bird and the observer to categorize behavioral
297 variables (Table 1).

298 We repeated nest approach experiments on separate days during the incubation period.
299 To avoid a possible cumulative effect of humans' presence on the bird's behavior, we
300 only considered data from nests that had not been previously visited by us on the same
301 day, and when humans had not been observed in the vicinity of the nest for at least one
302 hour before the experiment. For the same reason, we separated nest approaches at least
303 three days to minimize habituation to standardized disturbance stimuli (Gochfeld 1984;
304 Yasué and Dearden 2006; Muir and Colwell 2010).

305 Distraction displays usually start upon completion of egg-laying, although some birds
306 perform low intensity and risk displays during nest-scrape stage (e.g. vigilance behavior
307 or ground alarm calls). In this study, we only used the recorded behavioral displays
308 once nests had complete clutches. To account for a potential effect of parents'
309 investment in defensive behavior with increasing nest age, we conducted a preliminary
310 test between male and female ranked behavior against nest age (measured as days since
311 the first egg is laid). Since there were several approaching experiments per nest, we
312 randomly selected data of one approaching experiment per nest to avoid
313 pseudoreplication. These tests showed no relationship between nest age and defensive

314 behavior (Spearman rank correlation; male: $r_s = 0.003$, $N = 225$, $P = 0.959$; female: $r_s =$
315 0.002 , $N = 225$, $P = 0.980$). Additionally, in order to account for variations in distraction
316 behavior during the day, we conducted experiments in the morning and in the afternoon
317 on separate days.

318

319 **Data Analysis**

320 We used the nest survival model (Dinsmore et al. 2002; Dinsmore and Dinsmore 2007)
321 provided in Program MARK, version 8.0 (White and Burnham 1999) to estimate daily
322 survival rates (DSR) of nests and to examine the influence of temporal (e.g., year, time
323 of the nesting season, and nest age with respect to nesting season start), behavioral (nest
324 defense) and habitat variables on nest success.

325 Four input data are required to build the encounter histories for each nest in Program
326 MARK nest survival analysis: (1) day of the nesting season in which the nest was
327 found; (2) the last day the nest was active; (3) the day the nest was checked for the last
328 time; and (4) nest fate (0 = successful, 1 = failed) (Cooch and White 2014). We linked
329 each encounter history with covariates expected to influence nest survival (Table 2).
330 The covariates included the following: habitat type, distance to the seashore, substrate
331 type (binomial), degree of exposure (binomial) and human disturbance (binomial). Each
332 encounter history also included covariates for year and site.

333 Our interest was to explore the existence of a possible link between parental defensive
334 behavior and nest survival while taking into account the cumulative contribution of
335 these behaviors during the incubation period. To achieve this goal we analyzed the set
336 of different records of ranked behaviors, which we obtained during our visits to nests.

337 We used the ranked response to create a subset of ten new variables so as to integrate

338 them into survival models (Table 2). In species with biparental care, it is essential to
339 consider the defensive behavior of both members to assess the impact on reproductive
340 success (Burtka and Grindstaff 2015). Accordingly, we considered the additive effect of
341 defensive behavior exhibited by both sexes through the integration of the ranked
342 responses of males and females in different single variables for each nest.

343 We ranked a set of candidate models and compared them using Akaike's Information
344 Criterion (Akaike 1973) corrected for small sample sizes (AIC_c). We used ΔAIC_c values
345 and their relative normalized weights (w_i) to provide evidence of the relative support for
346 each model (Burnham and Anderson 2002). We assessed the importance of the
347 covariates included in the top-ranked models using beta estimates with standard errors
348 and 95% confidence intervals (CI) provided by Program MARK. Each covariate was
349 considered as biologically informative if confidence intervals did not overlap 0. Annual
350 estimates of nest success for each site were calculated by multiplying DSR to the 31st
351 exponent, consistent with the average maximum number of days that nests typically
352 survived (Amat and Masero 2004a).

353 We used a hierarchical model selection approach to identify the optimal predictive
354 model based in a 4-stage modelling procedure (Sexton and Farley 2012) (Table 2). We
355 identified the model that best fitted the data in each state, by assessing every additive
356 combination of different covariates of the same type. For each stage, the best fitted
357 model was used for the next stage of model building.

358 Firstly, we started model building with the simplest model, assuming that all nests had
359 the same DSR every day (i.e. a constant DSR over time). Secondly, we fitted models to
360 assess the relationship between DSR and time, considering linear trend (T) and
361 quadratic trend (TT). At this stage, we included effects of year, site and management

362 (human disturbance). In the second stage, we incorporated the effects of nest age (days)
363 relative to the start of the nesting season (NS), year and site. Thirdly, we added the
364 effect of nest age (days) in the day of the first encounter since the beginning of the
365 incubation period. In the fourth stage, we added habitat covariates (habitat type,
366 substrate, distance to the seashore and degree of exposure). In the final stage, we added
367 the behavior covariates of adults to the best model of the previous stages. We did not
368 evaluate the additive effects of the behavior of one sex (male or female) simultaneously
369 with variables describing total nest behavior (i.e., those including the behavior of male
370 and female jointly). The influence of each additive covariate in each candidate model
371 was assessed using the 95% CI provided by Program Mark (Burnham and Anderson
372 2002). No goodness-of-fit test is currently available for the nest survival models in
373 Mark program (Dinsmore et al. 2002; Cooch and White 2015).
374 Finally, Spearman's correlation analyses were conducted to assess the relationship
375 between ranked behaviors and nest survival (i.e., days active).

376

377 **RESULTS**

378 Overall, we monitored 327 nests during this study (1993-2001; 2007-2008): 242 at
379 Serradal beach, 29 at Almenara beach and 56 at Punta beach. The main causes for
380 clutch failure were predation (44.8%) and nest desertion (35.8%).

381

382 **Nest Defense**

383 There was a positive correlation between female and male mean ranked behaviors
384 within pairs (Spearman rank correlation: $r_s = 0.525$, $N = 225$, $P < 0.0001$; Fig. 1).
385 Nevertheless, there were differences in defensive behavior investment within the

386 breeding pair. Mean ranked behavior (\pm SE) were 1.40 ± 1.10 and 1.85 ± 1.18 for males
387 and females ($N = 225$ nests), respectively, and the difference between sexes was
388 significant (Wilcoxon signed-ranks test: $Z = -6.693$, $N = 225$, $P < 0.001$), with females
389 exhibiting riskier behavior.

390 The *ground alarm calls* behavior (i.e. ranked response 4) was seldom the riskiest
391 recorded behavior exhibited by both sexes, and was frequently followed by *mobile* or
392 *stationary distractions* (i.e. ranked responses 5 and 6, respectively). Nevertheless, the
393 latter display (i.e. ranked response 6) was more often performed by females than males
394 (11.61% of females and 0.89 % of males) (Wilcoxon signed-ranks test: $Z = -5.548$, $N =$
395 225 , $P < 0.001$).

396

397 **Nest Survival Models**

398 We created encounter histories for nest survival analysis in MARK for 225 nests, for
399 which we recorded all covariates. We developed 49 candidate models in the 4-stage
400 modelling procedure. The best model among multiple competing models resulting from
401 the three first stages and all models created in the final stage are shown in Table 3.

402 Our modelling results produced two models with $\Delta AIC_c < 2$ in the final stage of model
403 building, a single model with appreciable support ($\omega_i = 0.63$) and a second, less
404 competitive model ($\omega_i = 0.28$). Both models jointly had a high support from the model
405 set (summed $\omega_i = 0.90$; Table 3). The top-ranked models included nine parameters and
406 combined the additive effects of site, season (a quadratic trend time), habitat and
407 exposure. Both models were differentiated by the additive effects of behavioral
408 parameters considered. The top-ranked model included the additive effect of the
409 maximum value of female ranked behavior ($\beta = 0.52 \pm 0.11$, 95% CI = 0.32, 0.73; Table

410 4); the second model included the additive effect of the percentage of female ranked
411 behavior values higher than two ($\beta = 0.04 \pm 0.01$, 95% CI = 0.02, 0.05; Table 4).

412 Daily survival rate decreased as the breeding season progressed. Thus, nests that started
413 later in the season had a lower survival probability (Fig. 2). In the best model, we found
414 a strong positive relationship between DSR and the *maximum value of female ranked*
415 *behavior* (Table 4). Therefore, nests defended by females with riskier distraction
416 behaviors had greater DSR (Fig. 3). We also found a strong positive relationship
417 between DSR and the *embryonic shifting dunes* and *shifting dunes* habitats. Tidal debris
418 habitat had a weak positive relationship with DSR; the 95% CI of the estimate
419 overlapped 0. Finally, we also found a strong positive relationship between DSR and
420 *exposure*, with greater DSR for nests on unexposed nest-sites.

421 Covariates used to estimate the effect of the *Year*, *Management*, *Seashore*, *Nest_age*
422 and *Nest_season* (see variable description in Table 2) were not included in any of the
423 top ranked models. In the second ranked model, we found a weak positive relationship
424 between DSR and the *percentage of female ranked behavior values higher than two*,
425 which meant that nests defended by females who assumed more predation risk
426 throughout the incubation period had greater DSR (Fig. 3).

427

428 **DISCUSSION**

429 Our results show that Kentish plover's nests in which parents invested more on defense
430 survived longer, thus suggesting that defensive behaviors must play a critical role in
431 nest survival. Interestingly, we found differences in nest defense investment among
432 members of breeding pairs, with females performing riskier defensive behaviors than

433 males. In this respect, stationary distractions were performed by females in almost 12%
434 of the nests, but less than 1% by males.

435 Kentish plover females generally incubate during daytime (Fraga and Amat 1996),
436 although males also cooperate in situations of heat stress (Amat and Masero, 2004a;
437 AlRashidi et al. 2010). In our study, all experiences of nest approaching were performed
438 during daytime. Consequently, the lower response of males found in this study might be
439 accounted for by their absence from nests at the time our experiments were carried out.
440 Nevertheless, males and females were present (i.e., ranked response > 0) in 87.6% and
441 92.0% of the nests approaches, respectively. Furthermore, both sexes often displayed
442 defensive behavior, since there was some type of distraction display (average
443 percentage of ranked response > 2) in 55.1% and 69.8% of nests for males and females,
444 respectively. Sex differences in defense investment are common in birds, and females
445 normally perform more intense defensive behaviors, in accordance with their greater
446 reproductive investment (Montgomerie and Weatherhead 1988; Møller and Nielsen
447 2014). Nevertheless, the contribution of both sexes to nest defense in shorebirds should
448 have a direct link with nest survival, although this relationship has only been
449 demonstrated for species with biparental incubation (Smith and Wilson 2010).

450 Predator approaching and distraction displays are part of the Kentish plover's tactics to
451 assess risk and minimize predation. Birds inform their mate or chicks of potential
452 threats by emitting alarm calls or signals (Simmons 1955b). Under a more obvious
453 potential threat, parents may adopt other anti-predator tactics, such as distraction
454 displays (Gochfeld 1984). Our results showed that in 87.1% of nests at least one
455 member of the pair approached the observer and remained vigilant, performing some
456 type of active distraction displays in 74.2% of the studied cases (i.e. ranked response

457 >2). In this respect, both sexes emitted ground alarm calls initially, and very often this
458 was followed by riskier behaviors, such as mobile or stationary distraction displays.

459 Investment in anti-predator defense should be proportional to predation risk (Lima and
460 Dill 1990), but the effectiveness of distraction displays is probably linked to the risk
461 assumed (Sordahl, 1990b; Caro, 2005). Similar to our findings, Byrkjedal (1987)
462 showed that Eurasian dotterel, *Charadrius morinellus*, nests in which parents performed
463 stationary distraction displays had greater success than those in which parents
464 performed mobile displays only. Although the benefits of offspring defense are beyond
465 question, defensive behavior increases the probability of death or injury of adults, and
466 moreover reduces the available time for other reproductive duties (Walters 1982;
467 Montgomerie and Weatherhead 1988; Møller and Nielsen 2014). Notwithstanding, fatal
468 outcomes for birds performing distraction behaviors are expected to be rare, since high
469 risk behaviors would otherwise not be selected if the chances of a fatal outcome
470 outweighed benefits (Gochfeld 1984). In fact, only a few studies have documented cases
471 of birds being preyed upon while performing distraction behaviors (Sordahl, 1990a;
472 Brunton 1986). Nevertheless, although these predation events should be rare, their
473 importance should not be neglected (Brunton 1986; Lima and Dill, 1990; Sordahl
474 1990a; Lima 1993). Amat and Masero (2004a) described two cases of Kentish plovers
475 that were preyed upon while performing displays, one of them by a kestrel and the other
476 by dog. In our study area, we observed only one case of predation by a kestrel while
477 plovers were performing displays. Furthermore, domestic dogs were usually walked
478 along the studied beaches and frequently chased plovers, and this resulted in some nest
479 failures (Gómez-Serrano and López-López 2014). Indeed, we frequently observed dogs

480 attempting to capture plovers during distraction displays and we surmise that predation
481 by these animals could be significant.

482 Plovers avoid nesting in vegetated areas so as to increase predator detection (Page et al.
483 1985; Warriner et al. 1986; Martin 1988; Fraga and Amat 1996; Amat and Masero
484 2004a; Muir and Colwell 2010; Saalfeld et al. 2011; Anteau et al. 2012a; Gómez-
485 Serrano and López-López 2014). Hence, it is expected that birds nesting in exposed
486 sites will exhibit more intense defensive behaviors in order to compensate for the
487 greater detectability of their nests by predators (Larsen et al. 1996). On the other hand,
488 Amat and Masero (2004a) showed that females nesting in unexposed sites had a lower
489 body condition, presumably because they were unable to cope with the heat stress of
490 exposed locations. We found that *exposure* was a habitat covariate retained in the top-
491 ranked nest survival models, showing a strong positive relationship with DSR. Nests
492 located in unexposed sites had greater DSR. Nevertheless, contrary to our expectations,
493 males and females nesting in unexposed sites invested twice as much in nest defense
494 (mean % ranked response > 2; males: unexposed 31.2%, exposed 18.2%, Mann-
495 Whitney *U* test: $U = 4502.5$, $N = 225$, $P = 0.00056$; females: unexposed 39.4%, exposed
496 25.4%, Mann-Whitney *U* test, $U = 4654.0$, $N = 225$, $P = 0.00254$) as compared to those
497 nesting in exposed sites. This apparent contradiction can be accounted for by
498 environmental differences among both habitat types. Unlike the population studied by
499 Amat and Masero (2004a), which bred in an inland saline lake, plovers in our study area
500 bred on sandy beaches, where exposed nests were placed in vegetation free areas, in the
501 area comprised between shifting dunes and the seashore. These sites are exposed to the
502 sea breeze, which may have a thermoregulatory effect that alleviates heat stress on eggs
503 and the incubating adult (authors' unpubl. data). Thus, nests in unexposed sites might

504 experience higher temperatures and therefore be more vulnerable to egg or embryo loss
505 during prolonged absence of incubating adults. This might explain why birds nesting in
506 unexposed sites in our area performed more intense and risky distraction displays in
507 order to move the predator away as soon as possible, thus avoiding egg loss to
508 overheating.

509 Distraction behavior has been shown to vary depending on predator type (e.g. terrestrial,
510 aerial, mammal, etc.) (Byrkjedal 1987; Brunton 1990; Caro 2005; Šálek and Cepáková
511 2006), predator proximity (Sordahl 1986; Byrkjedal 1989) or the degree of risk assumed
512 by the bird while defending its offspring (Montgomerie and Weatherhead 1988;
513 Brunton 1990). For instance, distraction behavior is often displayed against ground
514 predators, particularly mammals, but seldom against avian predators (Armstrong 1954;
515 Byrkjedal 1989; Sordahl 1990b). Obviously, the bird assumes this risk posed by this
516 conduct because it ultimately contributes to increase its fitness. Consequently, the
517 intensity of distraction behaviors should be linked to the ability of the predator to
518 pinpoint its nest. In this respect, human presence was likely to elicit defensive behaviors
519 similar to those triggered by other terrestrial predators, since animals have developed
520 antipredator responses to generalized threatening stimuli (Frid and Dill 2002; Graham et
521 al. 2005). Indeed, humans are commonly used in studies dealing with offspring
522 defensive behavior (Byrkjedal 1987, 1989; Brunton 1990; Sordahl 1990b; Pavel et al.
523 2000; Lord et al. 2001; Brown and Brown 2004; Yasué and Dearden 2006; Møller and
524 Nielsen 2014). In a previous study, we found that birds modulate flushing behavior
525 depending on both predator type (i.e., higher response against people walking with
526 unleashed dogs than against people without dogs) and the intensity of human
527 disturbance, and that birds habituated to human presence tolerate closer approaches

528 (Gómez-Serrano and López-López 2014). Nevertheless, the selected models did not
529 include human disturbance. Indeed, there were no significant differences in the
530 defensive behavior of females and males among disturbed and undisturbed beaches
531 (mean ranked response; males: undisturbed 1.2, disturbed 1.5, Mann-Whitney U test, U
532 = 4207.0, $N = 225$, $P = 0.3243$; females: undisturbed 2.0, disturbed 1.8, Mann-Whitney
533 U test, $U = 3866.0$, $N = 225$, $P = 0.071$). This suggests that plovers consider humans as
534 potential predators (Roberts and Evans 1993; Schulz and Stock 1993; Webber et al.
535 2013) and, consequently, their presence triggers anti-predator responses of incubating
536 birds.

537 We found that the substrate on which nests were placed was not retained in the top-
538 ranked nest survival models. This contrasts with other studies on nest-site selection by
539 plovers, in which substrate type was linked to nest survival (Colwell et al. 2011; Anteau
540 et al. 2012b; Skrade and Dinsmore 2013). We hypothesize that the lack of relationship
541 between substrate and nest survival may be explained by the simplistic nature of the
542 variable used. Indeed, nest location was defined using a binary variable, which allowed
543 us to differentiate between nests on sand or pebbles. Nevertheless, even though egg
544 crypsis may differ between both substrates, other underlying factors could affect nest
545 detectability by predators, such as egg color, background matching (Lovell et al. 2013;
546 Skrade and Dinsmore 2013), substrate heterogeneity or frequency of egg-sized stones
547 (Colwell et al. 2011).

548 Individual behavioral differences may increase adult and offspring survival (Smith and
549 Blumstein 2008). The behavior of incubating birds may increase breeding success
550 through reducing predation risk of both adults and offspring. In this line, arctic
551 shorebirds taking fewer incubation recesses showed higher nest success, presumably as

552 a result of a lower detectability by predators (Smith et al. 2007, 2012). Other studies
553 reveal that flushing behavior of incubating shorebirds influenced nest survival (Koivula
554 and Rönkä 1998; Amat and Masero 2004a; Gómez-Serrano and López-López 2014).
555 Despite the importance that defensive behaviors of incubating adults may have on
556 breeding success, few studies have explored this relationship (Byrkjedal 1987; Smith
557 and Wilson 2010) and practically none have incorporated them as covariates in nest
558 survival models (Colwell et al. 2011). This situation is paradoxical, given the abundance
559 of studies on defensive behavior and short-term changes in predation risk (Frid and Dill
560 2002).

561 In conclusion, our study highlights that increased risk assumption in offspring defense
562 by adults is advantageous in terms of individual fitness, providing further insight into
563 the relative contribution of distraction displays on nest survival. On the other hand, the
564 greater investment in nest defense by females with regard to males revealed by our
565 experiments could be tentatively explained by greater investment in reproduction in the
566 case of females.

567

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- 778
- 779

780 **FIGURE LEGENDS**

781 **Figure 1.** Relationship between nest defense intensity (mean ranked behavior) of male
782 and female Kentish plovers within pairs ($N = 225$ nests).

783 **Figure 2.** Relationship between nesting season date and daily survival rates (black line)
784 with 95% confidence intervals (grey lines) of Kentish plover nests in the study area.

785 Day one corresponds to 14th March.

786 **Figure 3.** Daily survival rates (black line) with 95% confidence intervals (grey lines) of
787 Kentish plover nests in relation to female investment in defense behavior: maximum
788 recorded value of ranked behavior (left) and percentage of active distraction displays
789 (right).

790

791 **TABLES AND TABLE LEGENDS**792 **Table 1**

793 Ranked distraction behaviors of breeding Kentish Plovers in response to nest
 794 disturbance caused by an approaching researcher

Ranked response	Intensity of display	Summary behavior
0	Bird absent or early departure, without recorded return during the visit	Absent
1	Bird leaves the nest and flies to the shore or to an open site within its territory, from where it feeds or rests, but pays no further attention to the researcher.	Present
2	Bird flies or runs away, stopping at some distance (usually more than 15 meters) and watches the researcher from a place with good visibility	Vigilance behavior
3	Bird flies over or around the researcher and emits alarm calls	Flight alarm calls
4	Bird approaches the researcher (usually closer than 10 meters) emitting alarm calls	Ground alarm calls
5	Bird performs one of the following mobile distraction displays at a distance closer than 10 meters from the researcher: mobile lure-display with wings beating the ground (Simmons, 1951); incubation-feigning (i.e., the bird runs and then crouches onto the ground to simulate incubating or brooding duties; Gochfeld 1984; Caro 2005); rodent-run; simulating being injured bird (e.g. mobile broken-wing display) (Cramp and Simmons 1983; Gochfeld, 1984; Bergstrom, 1988)	Mobile distraction displays
6	Bird performs one of the following stationary lure-displays displays at a distance closer than 10 meters from the researcher: bird lies on ground while beating wings slowly; bird lies motionless while keeping its wings extended as if exhausted or shuffling wings spasmodically; bird lying while beating wings repeatedly rhythmically or spasmodically (Simmons 1951; Cramp and Simmons 1983)	Stationary distraction displays

796 **Table 2**

797 Description of the covariates related to habitat, season and behavior of plovers used in
 798 the nest survival models. The stage of the hierarchical modeling process in which the
 799 covariate is used is shown in the first column.

Modelling Stage	Abbreviated covariate	Description
1	Site	Serradal, Almenara and La Punta beaches
1	Year	Breeding season
1	Management	Human disturbance (1/0)
2	Nest_season	Nest age (days) on the first day of the nesting season (see Cooch and White, 2015 for more details)
2	Nest_age	Nest age (days) in the day of the first encounter since the beginning of the incubation period (see Cooch and White 2015 for more details)
3	Exposure	Nest exposure (1/0)
3	Seashore	Distance (m) to the seashore
3	Habitat	Habitat types
3	Substrate	Substrate types (1/0)
4	Male_behav	Average value of all records for male ranked behavior ranging from 0 (minimum value of nest defense) to six (maximum value)
4	Female_behav	Average value of all records for female ranked behavior ranging from 0 (minimum value of nest defense) to six (maximum value)
4	Nest_behav	Average of the maximum value of nest defense recorded for the male and the female in each visit (i.e., ranging from 0 to 6)
4	Total_nest_behav	Average value of all records for male and female ranked behavior (i.e., from 0 to 12)
4	%Male_behav	Percentage of male ranked behavior values higher than two (i.e. thus assuming higher risk)
4	%Female_behav	Percentage of female ranked behavior values higher than two

4	%Nest_behav	Percentage of nest ranked behavior values higher than two (the maximum value recorded during each visit for the male or the female was used)
4	Max_Male_behav	Maximum value of male ranked behavior
4	Max_Female_behav	Maximum value of female ranked behavior
4	Max_Nest_behav	Maximum value of nest ranked behavior (either male or female)

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802 **Table 3**

803 Selected models of Kentish plover nest survival analysis resulting from a 4-stage
 804 modelling procedure. The best model among multiple competing models resulting from
 805 the three first stages and all models created in the final stage are shown.

Modelling Stage	Model	AICc	Delta AICc	ω_i	Model Likelihood	K	Deviance
4	{B0+T*T+Site+Habitat+Exposure+ Max_Female_behav}	320.09	0	0.63	1	9	302.05
4	{B0+T*T+Site+Habitat+Exposure+%Female_behav}	321.74	1.65	0.28	0.43	9	303.70
4	{B0+T*T+Site+Habitat+Exposure+ Female_behav}	324.12	4.03	0.08	0.13	9	306.08
4	{B0+T*T+Site+Habitat+Exposure+ Max_Nest_behav}	329.37	9.28	0.006	0.01	9	311.33
4	{B0+T*T+Site+Habitat+Exposure+%Nest_behav}	330.35	10.25	0.004	0.006	9	312.32
4	{B0+T*T+Site+Habitat+Exposure+ Total_nest_behav}	331.59	11.50	0.002	0.003	9	313.55
4	{B0+T*T+Site+Habitat+Exposure+ Nest_behav}	332.44	12.35	0.001	0.002	9	314.40
4	{B0+T*T+Site+Habitat+Exposure+ Max_Male_behav}	341.60	21.51	0.00001	0	9	323.56
4	{B0+T*T+Site+Habitat+Exposure+%Male_behav}	342.23	22.14	0.00001	0	9	324.19
4	{B0+T*T+Site+Habitat+Exposure+ Male_behav }	345.07	24.98	0	0	9	327.03
3	{B0+T*T+Site+Habitat+Exposure}	345.77	25.68	0	0	8	329.74
1	{B0+T*T+Site}	356.01	35.92	0	0	4	348.0
2	{B0+T*T+Site+Nest_age}	356.61	36.52	0	0	5	346.60
	{B0}	374.65	54.56	0	0	1	372.65

806 Abbreviations: K = number of parameters; AICc = Akaike Information Criterion corrected for
 807 small sample size; ω_i = Akaike weights; T = Time; T*T = quadratic time trend. See variable
 808 description in Table 2.

809

810 **Table 4**

811 Model estimates from Program MARK of covariates included in the top-ranked models
 812 of daily survival rate of Kentish plover nests. The covariates were considered
 813 biologically informative if their confidence intervals did not include 0.

Parameter	B coefficient	SE	95% CI	
			Lower	Upper
Top-ranked model				
Intercept	0.024	0.993	-1.923	1.971
Quadratic time trend	-0.000	0.000	-0.000	-0.000
Site_Almenara	-2.047	0.590	-3.203	-0.891
Site_Serradal	0.177	0.454	-0.713	1.067
Habitat_tidal debris	1.050	0.578	-0.083	2.183
Habitat_embryonic shifting dunes	1.234	0.536	0.184	2.283
Habitat_shifting dunes	2.043	0.558	0.950	3.136
Exposure	1.999	0.531	0.958	3.040
Max_Female_behav	0.522	0.106	0.315	0.729
Second-ranked model				
Intercept	1.628	0.986	-0.304	3.560
Quadratic time trend	-0.000	-0.000	-0.000	-0.000
Site_Almenara	-2.289	0.608	-3.480	-1.097
Site_Serradal	-0.103	0.457	-0.998	0.793
Habitat_tidal debris	0.930	0.605	-0.256	2.117
Habitat_embryonic shifting dunes	1.118	0.551	0.038	2.198
Habitat_shifting dunes	1.960	0.548	0.886	3.034
Exposure	1.715	0.537	0.662	2.767
%Female_behav	0.036	0.008	0.019	0.053

814 Bold text denotes B coefficients with 95% CIs that did not overlap zero. See variable description in Table

815 2.

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817 FIGURES

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Figure 1

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Figure 2

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Figure 3

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